

Appendix A

GIS Database References

LIST OF EXHIBITS

<u>EXHIBIT TITLE</u>	<u>EXHIBIT NUMBER</u>
HISPANIOLA – GENERAL SOILS TYPE	A-1
HISPANIOLA – GENERAL LAND COVER	A-2
HAITI – PERMANENT AND TEMPORARY RIVER DIVERSION STRUCTURES	A-3
HAITI – EXISTING HYDROELECTRIC FACILITIES	A-4
HAITI – PREVIOUS STUDIES HYDROELECTRIC POTENTIAL	A-5

HISPANIOLA GENERAL SOILS TYPE

EXHIBIT A-1

LEGEND

LAND COVER		Open Shrublands	HAITI CITIES
Water	Woody Savannas	Savannas	Chef Lieu
Evergreen Needle leaf Forest	Grasslands	Capital	DOMINICAN REPUBLIC CITIES
Evergreen Broadleaf Forest	Permanent Wetland	Capital Departamento	Capital
Deciduous Needle leaf Forest	Croplands	GEO-POLITICAL BOUNDARIES	Departements
Deciduous Broadleaf Forest	Urban and Built-Up	Departamentos	
Mixed Forests	Cropland/Natural Vegetation		
Closed Shrublands			

HISPANIOLA GENERAL LAND COVER TYPE

RIVER DIVERSION STRUCTURES LIST

RIVER / STRUCTURE NAME	STRUCTURE TYPE
Acul	Permanent
Avezac	Permanent
Bassin General	Permanent
Caracol	Permanent
Cavaillon	Permanent
Desarmes	Permanent
La Pierre	Temporary
La Quinte	Temporary
Les Anglais	Temporary
Marrion	Permanent
Momance	Permanent
Onde Verte	Permanent
Onde Verte	Permanent
Peligre	Permanent
Ravine a Couleuvre	Permanent
Ravine Deux Bassins	Temporary
Riviere Barret	Permanent
Riviere Blanche	Permanent
Riviere Bouillie	Permanent
Riviere Bretelle	Permanent
Riviere Canot	Permanent
Riviere Coma	Permanent
Riviere Cotes de Fer	Permanent
Riviere Courjol	Permanent
Riviere de Henne	Permanent
Riviere Deluge	Permanent
Riviere des Bayonnais	Permanent
Riviere des Plantils	Temporary
Riviere Dupuy	Permanent
Riviere Fond Parisien	Permanent
Riviere Gaillard	Temporary
Riviere Gallois	Permanent
Riviere Gobe	Temporary
Riviere Gobe	Permanent
Riviere Gobe	Temporary
Riviere Jean Rabel	Permanent
Riviere Jean Rabel	Temporary
Riviere la Branle	Temporary
Riviere Lacoma	Permanent
Riviere l'Estere	Permanent
Riviere Matheux	Permanent
Riviere Millionnaire	Permanent
Riviere Mole Saint Nicolas	Permanent
Riviere Montrouis	Temporary
Riviere Moustiques	Permanent
Riviere Pascal	Permanent
Riviere Pascal	Permanent
Riviere Pierre Paillant	Permanent
Riviere Prien	Temporary
Riviere Saint Marc	Permanent
Riviere Tapion	Permanent
Riviere Torcelle	Temporary
Riviere Torcelle	Permanent
Riviere Trois Rivieres	Permanent
Riviere Veuve	Permanent
Rouyonne	Permanent
Saint Raphael	Permanent
Saut-Mathurine	Permanent

LEGEND

River Diversion Type

- ▲ Permanent
- ▲ Temporary

Cities

- ★ Capital
- ★ Chef Lieu

— Rivers

— Roads

■ Lakes

HAITI - PERMANENT AND TEMPORARY RIVER DIVERSION STRUCTURES

EXISTING HYDROELECTRIC FACILITIES LIST

FACILITY NAME	POWER (KW)	ESTIMATED ENERGY (KWH)	CLASS
Saut-Mathurine	1600	3,000,000	Macro
Gaillard	500	3,800,000	Mini
Deluge-Lanzac	1100	4,700,000	Small
Drouet	2500	6,000,000	Small
Peligre	54000	292,000,000	Large
Caracol	800	4,000,000	Mini
Onde Verde	300	1,900,000	Mini

TOTAL CAPACITY = 60,800 KW
 MAXIMUM POWER = 315,400,000 KWH
 ANNUAL ENERGY =

LEGEND

- Sites Classification
- Pico (P < 50 KW)
 - Micro (50 KW < P < 100 KW)
 - Mini (100 KW < P < 500 KW)
 - Small (500 KW < P < 1000 KW)
 - Macro (1000 KW < P < 10000 KW)
 - Large (P > 10000 KW)
- Cities
- ★ Capital
 - ★ Chef Lieu
 - Departements
 - Rivers
 - Roads
 - Lakes

HAITI - EXISTING HYDROELECTRIC FACILITIES

PREVIOUS STUDIES HYDROELECTRIC SITE LIST

SITE ID	FACILITY NAME	MAX. POWER (KW)	ESTIMATED ENERGY (KWH)	CLASS
HT001	Artibonite A109.1	20936	113,700,000	Large
HT002	Artibonite A139.9	28600	155,300,000	Large
HT003	Artibonite A4C	30000	162,900,000	Large
HT004	Bassin Bleu	129	320,000	Pico
HT005	Bouyaha B11	630	4,300,000	Mini
HT006	Bouyaha B66.1	460	3,100,000	Mini
HT007	Caracol	282	920,000	Micro
HT008	Cavaillon C42.3	240	1,300,000	Mini
HT009	Cazale 1UC	890	2,900,000	Mini
HT010	Cazale 2UC	470	1,700,000	Mini
HT011	Deluge-Lanzac	1180	3,250,000	Mini
HT012	Fer a Cheval FC34.1	190	1,300,000	Mini
HT013	Fer a Cheval FC8.5	740	4,500,000	Small
HT014	Gobe	190	730,000	Micro
HT015	Grande Anse BD8.6	1060	8,600,000	Small
HT016	Grande Anse BG15.4	2480	20,200,000	Macro
HT017	Grande Anse GA35.4	970	7,900,000	Small
HT018	Grande Anse GA4.1	1210	9,800,000	Macro
HT019	Grande Riviere de Nippes GNIP29.5	382	2,000,000	Mini
HT020	Grande Riviere du Nord GN30.3	720	4,900,000	Small
HT021	Grande Riviere du Nord GN47.7	480	3,200,000	Mini
HT022	Guayamouc GU25.7	2134	14,200,000	Macro
HT023	Guayamouc GU3.5	3408	7,400,000	Small
HT024	La Gosseline	153	360,000	Pico
HT025	La Theme LA1.6	1349	10,600,000	Macro
HT026	Limbe L27.1	520	4,300,000	Mini
HT027	Limbe L33.7	360	2,900,000	Mini
HT028	Momance	1120	3,500,000	Mini
HT029	Petite Riviere	130	419,000	Pico
HT030	Pichon	400	2,500,000	Mini
HT031	Pichon 2LC	680	5,300,000	Small
HT032	Riviere Grise G31.0	720	5,900,000	Small
HT033	Riviere Grise G41.1	379	2,000,000	Mini
HT034	Roche Plate	2570	9,810,000	Small
HT035	Samana	776	2,520,000	Mini
HT036	Saut d'Eau	670	5,740,000	Mini
HT037	Saut du Baril	365	1,230,000	Mini
HT038	Trois Rivières TR28	1778	14,200,000	Macro
HT039	Trois Rivières TR78	728	5,900,000	Small

TOTAL CAPACITY
 MAXIMUM POTENTIAL POWER = 110,479 KW
 ANNUAL POTENTIAL ENERGY = 602,800,000 KWH

LEGEND

Sites Classification

- Pico (P < 50 KW)
- Micro (50 KW < P < 100 KW)
- Mini (100 KW < P < 500 KW)
- Small (500 KW < P < 1000 KW)
- Macro (1000 KW < P < 10000 KW)
- Large (P > 10000 KW)

Cities

- ★ Capital
- ★ Chef Lieu
- Departements
- Rivers
- Roads
- Lakes

HAITI- PREVIOUS STUDIES HYDROELECTRIC POTENTIAL SITES